

Daily and Seasonal Variations of Water Vapor and High Clouds Observed From MODIS Data in the Near-IR Spectral Region

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INTRODUCTION

Several channels in the near-IR spectral region were implemented on the Moderate Resolution Imaging Spectroradiometer (MODIS) [1] [2] for remote sensing of water vapor and cirrus clouds from the Terra Spacecraft platform. Daily and seasonal variations of column atmospheric water vapor amounts have been observed reliably from MODIS channels located within and around the 0.94-micron water vapor band [3]. Daily and seasonal variations of high clouds have also been observed from the 1.375-micron cirrus-detecting channel [4]. This channel has an additional advantage – it allows significant improvement in detecting polar clouds during the daytime in comparison with channels on traditional meteorological satellites.

REMOTE SENSING OF WATER VAPOR

Remote sensing of water vapor profiles from space was traditionally made using IR emission channels. The results depended in part on the initial guess for the temperature and moisture profiles used in the inversion [5]. Column water vapor amounts over the ocean were retrieved from IR emission channels in the 11 - 13 μm spectral region using "split window" techniques [6] and from microwave emission measurements. The "split window" techniques also work well over land areas covered by green vegetation.

Several near-IR channels located within and around the 0.94- μm water vapor band were implemented on MODIS for remote sensing of column water vapor amounts over clear land areas of the globe, and above clouds over both land and ocean. These channels are also very useful for water vapor estimates over extended oceanic areas with sun glint. The retrieval algorithm relies on observations of water vapor attenuation of near-IR solar radiation reflected by surfaces and clouds. Techniques employing ratios of water vapor

absorbing channels at 0.865 and 1.24 micron are used. The ratios partially remove the effects of variation of surface reflectance with wavelengths and result in the atmospheric water vapor transmittances. The column water vapor amounts are derived from the transmittances based on theoretical radiative transfer calculations and using lookup table procedures. Water vapor values can be determined with errors typically in the range between 5% and 10%. The errors are greater for retrievals from data collected over dark surfaces or under hazy conditions.

SAMPLE WATER VAPOR RESULTS

Our algorithm has been used routinely for the retrieval of column water vapor amounts from MODIS data acquired during the daytime. The level 2 water vapor products are generated at the 1-km spatial resolution of the MODIS instrument. The daily, 8-day, and monthly level 3 water vapor products are computed on one degree by one degree latitude and longitude grids.

Figure 1 shows an example of level 3 water vapor products. It is a global water vapor image of the monthly mean for September of 2000. The water vapor values over the India continent are quite large, while those over the high altitude Tibet Plateau are very small. There is a sharp boundary between the India continent and Tibet Plateau. Figure 2 shows a global water vapor image of the monthly mean for December of 2000. By comparing this image with the image in Fig. 1, it is seen that the water vapor values over continental areas in the northern hemisphere in December are significantly smaller than those in September because of lower temperature in the northern hemisphere in December.

REMOTE SENSING OF CIRRUS CLOUDS

Because of their partial transparency, thin cirrus clouds are difficult to detect in satellite images, particularly over land,

both in the visible and in the 10-12 micron IR atmospheric window regions. Through analysis of hyperspectral imaging

Fig. 1: A monthly-mean global water vapor image for September of 2000.

Fig. 2: A monthly-mean global water vapor image for December of 2000.

data collected by the Airborne Visible Infrared Imaging Spectrometer (AVIRIS), it was found that narrow channels near the center of the strong 1.38-micron water vapor band are very effective in detecting thin cirrus clouds [7]. The mechanism is as follows. In the absence of cirrus clouds, these channels receive little scattered solar radiation from the surface and from lower-level clouds because of nearly total absorption by atmospheric water vapor. When cirrus clouds are present, however, these channels receive solar radiance scattered by the upper level cirrus clouds. Based on this observation, a special channel centered at 1.375 micron with a width of 30 nm was selected and implemented on the MODIS instrument for remote sensing of cirrus clouds from space [4].

SAMPLE CIRRUS CLOUD RESULTS

Similar to our near-IR water vapor algorithm, our cirrus detection algorithm [8] has been used operationally for the retrieval of cirrus reflectances from MODIS data acquired during the daytime. The level 2 and level 3 cirrus reflectance data products are routinely generated at the NASA Goddard Data Center.

Figure 3 shows an example of level 3 cirrus reflectance products. It is a global cirrus reflectance image of the monthly mean for August of 2000. Cirrus clouds in polar regions are seen obviously in this image. Such cirrus detection is very difficult from NOAA AVHRR data due to the lack of water vapor absorption channels on the AVHRR instruments. Cirrus clouds in the latitude range between 10 and 20 degrees in the northern hemisphere are also seen obviously. These clouds are likely due to evaporation of sea water by solar heating and subsequent freezing of water vapor into ice particles at high altitudes (near the tropopause).

Fig. 3: A monthly-mean global cirrus reflectance image for August of 2000.

SUMMARY

The MODIS instrument has implemented several near-IR channels for remote sensing of water vapor and cirrus clouds. Our products derived from MODIS data will have important applications in meteorology, hydrology, and climatology.

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